

Monitoring of pesticide residue levels in Lebanese table grapes from 2012-2014 and human health risk assessment

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Abstract

In many countries, pesticide residue monitoring is regularly conducted in food by health organizations. In Lebanon, the lack of monitoring data on grapes has significant drawbacks for human health and economic impact. To address this, the Ministry of Agriculture in Lebanon conducted a monitoring campaign of pesticide residue levels in Lebanese table grapes between 2012 and 2014. For this study, 1,594 Lebanese table grape samples were collected from the main wine-growing regions. Among the 80 pesticides analyzed, 48 molecules were detected. Over 56% of grape samples contained pesticide residues, and 16% exceeded Codex Alimentarius MRLs. The median concentration of pesticide residues in 2012 (0.18 mg.kg⁻¹) was significantly higher than in 2013 (0.06 mg.kg⁻¹) and 2014 (0.07 mg.kg⁻¹). Pesticides with a systemic mode of action dominated (>78%), and fungicides were the prevalent functional class (>73%). The risk assessment indicated a low risk for adults and children (HQ < 1), however our HQ calculation did not take into account the presence of these molecules in foods other than grapes. Furthermore, the frequent detection of pesticide cocktails (>27%) in grapes could result in potential antagonistic and synergistic effects, and therefore a higher risk than that assessed by the HQ.

Key-words: *Fungicide, Insecticide, LCMSMS, GCMSMS, QuEChERS, Grapevine Disease, Pest Management*

1. Introduction

Grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) is a significant global crop, covering 7.4 million hectares worldwide in 2018 and producing 77.8 million tons of grapes (Arkam et al., 2021). Mediterranean countries account for the largest viticultural area, with 4.2 million hectares (Capon et al., 2014), where viticulture is essential for economic growth and cultural heritage (Daniele and Paolo, 2023; João et al., 2024). However, the sector faces growing threats from climate change, which increase vineyards' vulnerability to diseases, especially cryptogamic ones (Bois et al., 2017; Jaume et al., 2022; Lia-Tânia et al., 2022).

To combat these threats, vineyards often undergo frequent pesticide treatments, especially with fungicides, sometimes up to 10 times per season (Zubrod et al. 2019). For example, in 2020, Italian vineyards received an average of 24.89 kilograms of pesticides per hectare (ISTAT, 2023), while Spain's usage was even higher at 34.2 kg/ha (Alonso González et al., 2021; Alonso González et al., 2022). In France, the average was 17 kg/ha (Fouillet et al., 2022). Consistently, studies have reported high levels of pesticide residues in grapes. For instance, 2.6% of grape samples imported from Italy exceeded European Union Maximum Residue Limits (MRLs) (Poulsen et al., 2007), while in Egypt, 87% of tested grape samples contained pesticide residues, with 39% above Codex Alimentarius MRLs (Elmarsafy and Kadah, 2018). Similar findings were observed in Tunisia (Bouagga et al., 2019) and Turkey (Golge and Kabak, 2018).

In Lebanon, table grapes are a major crop, with an annual production of 120,000 tons (CBI, 2018) and exports exceeding 21 million dollars in 2020 (Trade, 2022). However, a study revealed that grapes sold in the capital -Beirut- were among the most contaminated plant-based foods, with 3.1% of 387 samples testing positive for pesticide residues (Khazaaal et al., 2022). Nearly 50% of agricultural farms in Lebanon overuse pesticides, leading to significant environmental and health risks (Akkouch and Halwani, 2023), with some areas applying doses up to 100 times higher than recommended (Akkouch and Halwani, 2023). The excessive use of pesticides is driven by weak regulatory enforcement, limited resources, poverty, and lack of knowledge. Additionally, the continued use of banned pesticides (Koubeissy, 2014; Abou Zeid et al., 2020) and fragmented regulatory oversight further complicate effective control (Abou Zeid et al., 2020).

Despite the importance of viticulture in Lebanon, limited data exists on pesticide

residue levels in table grapes and the associated health risks. To address these gaps, Lebanon's Ministry of Agriculture implemented the "Activating Production Chains" strategy from 2010 to 2014, aiming to improve production quality and enhance competitiveness (Hobeika and El Khouri, 2011). As part of this initiative, a pesticide residue monitoring campaign for grapes was launched in 2012, accompanied by training workshops on Good Agricultural Practices (GAPs). This campaign enabled the collection of unprecedented data on pesticide residues in 1,594 table grape samples across Lebanon's four wine regions (Bekaa, North, Mount Lebanon, and South) over three years (2012 to 2014). The study was authorized for research and publication by the Minister of Agriculture (authorization number 3/7804, October 19, 2018). The primary objectives of this study were to monitor pesticide residue levels in Lebanese table grapes from 2012 to 2014 and assess the associated human health risks across the four wine-growing regions.

2. Material and Methods

Grape sampling across Lebanese Regions

Grape samples were collected from 2012 to 2014, covering the four main viticultural regions in Lebanon: Bekaa (including Bekaa and Baalbeck-El Hermel Governorates; total area: 444,200 ha; table grape area: 10,000 ha), the North (North and Akkar Governorates; total area: 202,400 ha; table grape area: 213 ha), Mount Lebanon (including Mount Lebanon and Jbeil-Keserwan Governorates; total area: 195,800 ha; table grape area: 500 ha), and the South (including South and Nabatieh Governorates; total area: 198,800 ha; table grape area: 761 ha) (Figure II-1).

Sampling and samples handling were realized according to FAO/WHO guidelines (FAO/WHO 2023) regarding the methods of sampling [CAC/GL 33-1999], the amounts of grapes to be analyzed [CAC/GL 41-1993] and the good laboratory practice in pesticide residue analysis [CAC/GL 40-1993]. Two-kilogram samples were collected from each monitored vineyard regardless its surface area by employees of the Ministry of Agriculture in the regional departments and/or by grape producers, following clauses 2, 3, and 4 of Decision No. 380 of the Ministry of Agriculture (MoA 2012). From each 2 kg grape sample, a 1 kg subsample was placed in a sealed polyethylene bag with proper labeling and a specific ID, and then sent directly to the Kfarshima Laboratory for pesticide analysis. The total number of grape samples

collected was 588 in 2012, 425 in 2013, and 581 in 2014.

Figure II- 1: Distribution of the number of samples across the Lebanese Regions

Samples handling, pesticide residues extraction and analysis

All pesticide extraction then analyses were done within 3 days from the arrival of the samples to Kfarshima Laboratory. The 1 kg grape sample was grinded and homogenized using a VCM4 Waring Vertical Cutter Blender/Mixer 309 (Halde, Sweden) and 10 grams were taken and put in 50 ml polypropylene centrifuge tubes. The pesticide residues QuEChERS extraction and analysis of 80 pesticides (Annexe I - Table SII-1) by LCMSMS and GCMSMS was done as previously reported by Khazaal et al. 2022. In regards to the method performance criteria, during the period of residues analysis (2012-2014), SANCO/12495/2011 guidelines (EC 2023) were officially adopted by the Reference ministry accredited Laboratory Kfarchima. Thus, the performance of the method was assessed according to the following criteria: linearity ($R^2 > 0.98$), recovery (RM%) between 70–120%, within-laboratory repeatability ($RSDr\% \leq 20\%$) and reproducibility ($RSDRW\% \leq 20\%$). The Limits of Detection (LOD) and Quantification (LOQ) were established at 0.01 mg/kg for all the molecules.

Pesticide properties

The mode of action for pesticides was obtained from the Global Resistance Management

Mode of Action (IRAC 2023), and their properties were sourced from the PPDB database (Lewis et al., 2016). The PPDB (2023) alert system categorizes pesticides as high, moderate, or low risk based on their environmental fate (including persistence in soil, leaching potential, potential for loss via drain flow, and potential for particle-bound transport), ecotoxicity (acute and chronic toxicity to birds, fish, daphnia, bees, and earthworms), and human health effects (including acute and chronic mammalian toxicity, carcinogenicity, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption, reproductive and developmental effects, acetylcholinesterase inhibition, and neurotoxicity). A pesticide is assigned a high alert if any of its evaluated properties is classified as "High" (PPDB 2023).

Data Analysis

The data was analyzed using the R free software and multiple relevant packages. The dataset was summarized using descriptive statistical techniques like mean, median, standard deviation (SD), range (min-max), and count (N). Since the sample sizes were unequal across the years and regions, the Kruskal-Wallis test was employed to assess the significance of the concentration differences among 2012, 2013, and 2014. To conduct pairwise comparisons, the Dunn-test was utilized. The Dunn-test is particularly suitable for situations where sample sizes are unequal.

Health Risk Assessment

In order to evaluate the risk of pesticide residues in grapes to human health, calculations for HQ (hazard quotient) were performed. HQ estimations are utilized to assess the chronic effects of residues. A value exceeding 1 for HQ would indicate a potential risk to human health. To calculate HQ, the estimated daily intake (EDI) was determined using the following equation (1):

$$EDI = \sum \frac{F_i \times MR_i}{Bw} \quad (1)$$

where EDI = the estimated daily intake (in milligrams per kilogram per day)

F_i = the daily grape consumption data (kg)

MR_i = the mean residual pesticide concentration (mg/kg)

Bw = the body weight of the consumer (kg).

For adults, a body weight of 63 kg and grape consumption of 0.00635 kg/day were assumed (EFSA 2023). For children, a body weight of 16 kg and grape consumption of 0.0131 kg/day were considered (EFSA 2023).

HQ values were obtained using equation (2):

$$HQ = (EDI/ADI) \quad (2).$$

ADI = the acceptable daily intake (in milligrams per kilogram per day) (obtained from the PPDB database, Lewis et al., 2016).

3. Results and Discussion

Grape Samples Collected

The number of grape samples collected varied significantly across the four Lebanese regions, with a notable focus on the Bekaa and North regions. The Bekaa region, being the center of Lebanese agriculture and hosting the largest viticultural area in Lebanon (10,000 ha), had the highest number of samples collected: 469 in 2012, 262 in 2013, and 420 in 2014. In contrast, the North region, despite having a smaller viticultural area of 213 ha compared to the South (761 ha) and Mount Lebanon (500 ha), also had a considerable number of samples collected: 102 in 2012, 146 in 2013, and 122 in 2014 (see Fig. II-1). The lower number of samples from South Lebanon, with 17, 14, and 25 samples in 2012, 2013, and 2014 respectively, and from Mount Lebanon, with 0, 3, and 14 samples over the same years, may be attributed to different levels of engagement among grape producers. Producers in the Bekaa and North regions may have been more proactive in submitting samples for analysis and reporting their intentions to export their grape production, thereby falling under the monitoring activities of the Ministry of Agriculture.

Pesticide Residue Occurrences and levels in grapes

Across all 4 Lebanese regions, the presence of pesticide residues was observed in 97%, 63%, and 56% of samples in 2012, 2013, and 2014, respectively (Table II-1). Among these samples, 33%, 17%, and 16% showed levels of one or more pesticides above the Codex Alimentarius MRLs, and therefore were classified as rejected by the Ministry of Agriculture (Table II-1). The number of grape samples with residues and without residues across Lebanese regions in 2012, 2013 and 2014 is given in Annexe I - Table SII-2. In addition, the range of concentrations, mean concentration with standard deviation, median concentration, as well as the incidence of MRL exceedances for each molecule detected during the years 2012, 2013, and 2014 are given in Annexe I - Table SII-3.

Table II- 1: Frequency of detection of pesticide residues across the four regions in 2012, 2013, and 2014

			2012	2013	2014
Samples	Frequency of detection of pesticide residues	<i>Bekaa</i>	810	302	592
		<i>North</i>	270	205	150
		<i>South</i>	4	21	31
		<i>Mount-Lebanon</i>	0	2	20
	Status* (%)	<i>RD</i>	97.5	63.1	55.9
		<i>NRD</i>	2.5	36.9	44.1
		<i>Accepted</i>	67.0	82.6	83.8
		<i>Rejected</i>	33.0	17.4	16.2
Molecules**	Mode of action (%)	<i>Contact</i>	21.3	9.1	12.4
		<i>Systemic</i>	77.9	89.4	86.4
		<i>Contact and systemic</i>	0.7	1.5	1.3
	Functional class (%)	<i>Fungicide</i>	73.0	84.5	76.2
		<i>Insecticide</i>	26.7	15.5	23.8
		<i>Acaricide</i>	0.2	0.0	0.0
		<i>Herbicide</i>	0.1	0.0	0.0
	Legal status in Lebanon in 2023 (%)	<i>Approved</i>	72.2	78.1	78.8
		<i>Not approved</i>	27.0	21.1	21.2
		<i>Pending</i>	0.7	0.7	0
	Legal status in EU in 2023 (%)	<i>Approved</i>	60.6	66.2	75.2
		<i>Not approved</i>	39.4	33.8	24.8
	Classification according to the World Health Organization (WHO) (%)	<i>Ib</i>	0.5	0	0.1
		<i>II</i>	40.1	39.4	39.2
		<i>III</i>	8.6	4.5	5.5
		<i>U</i>	39.6	47.4	44.9
		<i>Not Listed</i>	11.2	8.7	10.2
	Recommended (%)	<i>Yes</i>	80.7	78.7	74.0
		<i>No</i>	19.3	21.3	26.0
	*RD : residues detected ; NRD: no residues detected; Accepted samples are samples with residues < Codex MRLs; Rejected samples are samples with residues > Codex MRLs.				
**Legal status in 2023; To be used on grapes according to the European phytosanitary index; For WHO classification: Ib: highly hazardous, II: moderately hazardous, III: slightly hazardous, U: unlikely to present an acute hazard, Not Listed: Not listed in WHO classification; Recommended: by the Ministry of Agriculture in Lebanon according to its 2010-2014 strategy guide for table grape producers.					

Among the 80 molecules investigated, the analysis showed the presence of 48 pesticides (Annexe I -Table SII-3). The median concentration in 2012, was significantly higher (0.18 mg.kg⁻¹) than the median concentrations in 2013 (0.06 mg.kg⁻¹) and 2014 (0.07 mg.kg⁻¹), with no significant difference between the latter two, as determined by Kruskal-Wallis - Dunn tests (Figure II-2). Details of the pesticides concerned and their levels are shown in the Annexe I - Figure SII-1. The observed decline in median pesticide concentration is likely due to improved

practices encouraged by the issued guide by the Ministry of Agriculture, enhanced awareness and training for viticulturists, and stricter regulatory enforcement and monitoring. However, the percentage of residues from banned molecules increased to reach 26% of the detected molecules in 2014 (table II-1). This increase in the occurrence of banned molecules may be attributed to the war in Syria (2011-2021), which has resulted in loose border controls. These conditions have facilitated the smuggling of forbidden and unregistered pesticide products across the border, allowing them to be sold at cheaper prices.

Figure II- 2: Median pesticide concentrations (mg/kg) in grapes for the three years and Kruskal-Wallis - Dunn tests results

Figure II-3 illustrates molecules detected more than 20 times per year from 2012 to 2014. Among these frequently detected molecules, Thiophanate-methyl, Cypermethrin, and Difenoconazole, pesticide recommended in the Ministry of Agriculture's guide consistently exceeded MRLs over the three years. Specifically, Thiophanate-methyl exceeded Codex MRLs in 76%, 79%, and 71% of instances, while Cypermethrin exceeded MRLs in 64%, 81%, and 97% of instances in 2012, 2013, and 2014 respectively. Similarly, Difenoconazole exceeded MRLs in 18%, 33%, and 38% of instances over the same period. Yet it is speculated that viticulturists did not adhere to the recommended dose per hectare specified on the product label and/or to pre-harvest intervals, the minimum required time prior to harvest that allows residues to fall below MRLs, resulting in inadequate adoption of GAPs to avoid MRL exceedances. Additionally, forbidden molecules such as Acetamiprid and Tetraconazole were frequently

detected with MRL exceedances. Acetamiprid showed MRL exceedances in 44% and 35% of instances in 2012 and 2013 respectively, this molecule was also frequently detected in 2014 (73 occurrences) although at levels below MRLs. Tetraconazole was only detected in 2014 with MRL exceedances in 31% of instances. Chlorpyrifos also exhibited MRL exceedances in 52% of instances, but only in 2014. These results highlight the non-compliance with regulations in terms of authorized molecules and doses applied. The implementation of agricultural logbooks could be a way to improve the traceability of the molecules used as well as the doses applied.

Figure II- 3: Frequently detected pesticides in grapes samples (>20 times) and their MRLs exceedances in 2012, 2013 and 2014

Types of the Molecules, Functional Class and Chemical Family

Regarding the types of the molecules according to their mechanism of action it becomes evident that systemic pesticides were consistently prevalent across the study years, accounting for 78% in 2012, 89% in 2013, and 86% in 2014 (Table II-1). This observation is of concern since systemic pesticides are suspected to have sublethal health effects on humans and contribute to the widespread contamination on the environment (Sánchez-Bayo, Goka, and Hayasaka 2016; Odewale et al. 2022).

According to their functional class, there was a noticeable predominance of fungicides, constituting 73% in 2012, 85% in 2013, and 76% in 2014, compared to insecticides (24-27 %); acaricides and herbicides were only present in 2012 although in less than 0.2 % of incidences (Table II-1). These findings align with results from table grape monitoring in other Mediterranean countries. In Tunisia, 60.7% of the detected molecules in table grape samples were fungicides (Bouagga et al. 2019). In Turkey, 87.5% of the quantifiable molecules were

fungicides (Golge and Kabak 2018). Similarly, in the Czech Republic, 89.7% of the detected pesticide residues were fungicides, aligning with the results of this study in terms of the nature and functional class of the molecules detected (Schusterova et al. 2021). The estimated mean concentration of fungicides in table grape was the highest in 2012 (0.46 mg/kg) followed by 2014 (0.36 mg/kg) and 2013 (0.28 mg/kg) (Table II-2). The total concentration of insecticide in table grape was significantly lower than fungicides with average concentrations from 0.26 to 0.30 mg/kg. The detected fungicides were employed primarily targeted powdery mildew, followed by downy mildew and grey mold. In the case of insecticides, aphids were the primary target. Annexe I - Figure SII-3 illustrates the frequency of pesticide treatments.

Table II- 2: Average pesticide residue levels (mg/kg) in table grapes according to their functional class, chemical family, sampling region and sampling year

		2012				2013				2014			
		Mean Concentration in mg/kg \pm SD											
Functional Class	Chemical Family	Bekaa	North	South	Mount-Lebanon	Bekaa	North	South	Mount-Lebanon	Bekaa	North	South	Mount-Lebanon
Fungicides	Anilinopyrimidine	0.38 \pm 0.28	0.47 \pm 0.34	0.07	NS	0.17 \pm 0.21	0.15 \pm 0.11	0.20	<LOD	0.27 \pm 0.36	0.37 \pm 0.34	0.64 \pm 0.48	0.47 \pm 0.39
	Benzimidazole	0.82 \pm 0.70	0.68 \pm 0.60	<LOD	NS	0.85 \pm 1.31	0.42 \pm 0.81	0.18 \pm 0.11	0.30 \pm 0.14	0.54 \pm 1.68	0.52 \pm 0.69	0.74 \pm 0.49	1.21
	Carboxamide	1.33 \pm 1.08	0.21 \pm 0.21	0.07	NS	0.09 \pm 0.05	0.11 \pm 0.07	0.12 \pm 0.03	<LOD	0.32 \pm 0.43	0.27 \pm 0.18	0.63 \pm 0.57	0.42 \pm 0.59
	Cyanoacetamide oxime	0.01	<LOD	<LOD	NS	<LOD							
	Dicarboximide	<LOD	0.01 \pm 0.00	<LOD	NS	<LOD							
	Hydroxyanilide	0.49 \pm 0.49	0.93 \pm 0.54	<LOD	NS	0.45 \pm 0.60	0.53 \pm 0.74	<LOD	<LOD	0.50 \pm 0.63	<LOD	0.26 \pm 0.11	<LOD
	Morpholine	0.04	<LOD	<LOD	NS	0.03 \pm 0.01	<LOD						
	Phenylamide	0.19 \pm 0.18	0.15 \pm 0.13	<LOD	NS	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.13 \pm 0.18	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	Strobilurin	0.31 \pm 0.33	0.35 \pm 0.35	0.04 \pm 0.01	NS	0.21 \pm 0.41	0.11 \pm 0.15	0.11 \pm 0.12	<LOD	0.11 \pm 0.13	0.14 \pm 0.13	0.20 \pm 0.17	<LOD
	Triazole	0.13 \pm 0.21	0.17 \pm 0.32	<LOD	NS	0.15 \pm 0.19	0.12 \pm 0.14	0.12 \pm 0.04	<LOD	0.53 \pm 1.25	0.38 \pm 0.91	0.53 \pm 1.14	1.68 \pm 2.04
Mean fungicides level by region		0.46 \pm0.62	0.50 \pm0.53	0.052 \pm0.02	NA	0.33 \pm0.72	0.21 \pm0.42	0.14 \pm0.08	0.30 \pm0.14	0.34 \pm0.88	0.33 \pm0.58	0.50 \pm0.66	0.96 \pm1.41
Mean fungicides level by year		0.46 \pm0.60				0.28 \pm0.61				0.36 \pm0.85			
Insecticides	Benzoylurea	0.15 \pm 0.17	0.27	<LOD	NS	<LOD	0.39 \pm 0.01	<LOD	<LOD	0.17 \pm 0.29	0.43 \pm 0.28	1.36	<LOD
	Carbamate	0.09	<LOD	<LOD	NS	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.004	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD

		±0.10											
	Diphenyl oxazoline	<LOD	0.09	<LOD	NS	<LOD							
	Neonicotinoid	0.37 ±0.31	0.25 ±0.25	<LOD	NS	0.20 ±0.27	0.31 ±0.25	<LOD	<LOD	0.14 ±0.12	0.17 ±0.14	0.07 ±0.07	0.05
	Organophosphate	0.23 ±0.20	0.22 ±0.19	<LOD	NS	0.29 ±0.51	0.20 ±0.05	<LOD	<LOD	0.46 ±0.42	0.27 ±0.22	0.13	<LOD
	Oxadiazine	0.24 ±0.27	0.43 ±0.38	<LOD	NS	0.15 ±0.01	0.11 ±0.02	<LOD	<LOD	0.33 ±0.23	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
	Pyrethroid	0.38 ±0.35	0.81 ±0.52	<LOD	NS	0.33 ±0.25	0.25 ±0.14	0.30 ±0.08	<LOD	0.35 ±0.22	0.46 ±0.26	<LOD	0.30
	Pyridazinone	0.02 ±0.04	0.05 ±0.06	<LOD	NS	<LOD	0.01	0.003	<LOD	0.01	0.01 ±0.00	<LOD	<LOD
	Sulphite ester	2.40 ±0.57	<LOD	<LOD	NS	<LOD							
Mean insecticides level by region		0.30 ±0.36	0.30 ±0.35	NA	NA	0.26 ±0.30	0.26 ±0.20	0.23 ±0.16	NA	0.27 ±0.30	0.26 ±0.23	0.34 ±0.57	0.17 ±0.17
Mean insecticides level by year		0.30 ±0.35				0.26 ±0.24				0.27 ±0.29			
Herbicides	Aryloxyphenoxypropionate	0.01	<LOD	<LOD	NS	<LOD							
Mean herbicide level by region		0.01	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Mean herbicide level by year		0.01 ±NA				NA				NA			
Mean pesticide level by region		0.41 ±0.56	0.45 ±0.50	0.01 ±0.02	NA	0.24 ±0.61	0.17 ±0.35	0.13 ±0.11	0.20 ±0.20	0.24 ±0.70	0.23 ±0.46	0.34 ±0.60	0.68 ±1.24
Mean pesticide level by year		0.41 ±0.54				0.21 ±0.51				0.25 ±0.67			

*SD : Standard Deviation ; NS : No Samples; LOD: Limit of Detection; NA: Not Applicable

It is of significance to note that, in the year 2012, the residues of fungicides exhibited a clear predominance of the triazole chemical family (223 residues), followed by the benzimidazole chemical family (167 residues) and the strobilurin chemical family (159 residues). Similarly, in 2013, these same three chemical family continued to dominate, with 140 residues attributed to the triazole family, 104 to the strobilurin family, and 88 to the benzimidazole family. However, in the subsequent year, 2014, a noticeable shift occurred as the carboxamide family emerged as the third most prevalent among fungicides, comprising 123 residues. The strobilurin group retained its prominence with 160 residues, while the triazole family accounted for 153 residues. Regarding insecticides, the residues primarily belonged to three key chemical family: organophosphates, neonicotinoids, and pyrethroids (Annexe I - Figure SII-4).

Application repeated from one year to the next of the same chemical family, particularly benzimidazole and triazoles, contributes to the emergence of resistant fungal populations, especially *B. cinerea* (grey mold) that is one of the main diseases attacking grape vines in Lebanon. Shao, Zhao, and Ma (2021) reported that benzimidazole-resistant *B. cinerea* (grey

mold) populations became dominant in China. A similar situation applies to triazoles, with resistant populations of *Uncinula necator* (powdery mildew) being reported since 2000 in South Africa vineyards (Halleen and Holz 2017).

In addition, for the 3 years and all regions, the insecticide contents were the highest for the organophosphates and pyrethroids chemical family (Annexe I - Table SII-4) which are frequently detected in surface and ground-water in Lebanon (Akkouch and Halwani 2023). These repeated treatments of fungicides and insecticides therefore generate not only risks of pest resistance but also risks to human health. In Lebanon, a study revealed that many agricultural workers are unaware of the safety rules regarding the use of pesticides (Salameh et al. 2004). This lack of awareness exposes both agricultural workers and consumers to unsafe levels of pesticide residues.

Occurrence of Multiresidue Samples

Figure II-4 provides clear evidence of the presence of samples containing multiple residues (reaching 9 residues) throughout the years 2012, 2013, and 2014. The majority of these samples consisted of two residues, representing 27% in 2012, 32 % in 2013, and 29% in 2014. Less than 3% of the samples contained as many as nine residues in 2014. For instance, one of the cocktails (9 residues) obtained in 2014 contained 2 molecules with a mode of action targeting acetylcholinesterase (Acetamiprid, Chlorpyrifos), 2 molecules targeting the tubulin polymerization (Carbendazim, Thiophanate-methyl), 3 DeMethylation Inhibitors (Difenoconazole, Penconazole, Tetraconazole), 1 sodium channel inhibitor (Cypermethrine), and 1 targeting the respiration - Quinone outside Inhibitors (Azoxytrobine). The presence of several molecules with the same mode of action class in these cocktails contributes to resistance in agents causing grapevine diseases, leading to increased usage of phytosanitary products (IRAC 2023). In pests, the use of pesticides with the same mode of action leads to resistance through various mechanisms, including behavioral, penetration, metabolic, and altered target-site resistances (Massi, Torriani, Borghi, and Toffolatti, 2021). These findings highlight the need to train Lebanese viticulturists about pesticide to avoid repetitive and simultaneous use of pesticides with the same mode of action. Furthermore, the implementation of integrated pest control techniques would make it possible to reduce the quantities of pesticides applied to vineyard plots.

Figure II- 4: Percentage of grape samples containing one or more pesticide residues in 2012,2013, and 2014

Toxicity of the detected pesticides

In our study, around 43% of the detected molecules over the three years were found to be unlikely to present an acute hazard according to the WHO hazard classification (category U), whereas 39% of those fell under the category II – moderately hazardous - which refers to molecules having a lethal dose fifty (LD50) between 50 and 500 mg/kg; meanwhile 6% fell under the slightly hazardous category (III), 0.2 % under the highly hazardous category (Ib) and around 10 % were not listed in the WHO classification (WHO 2019) (Table II-1).

Additionally, an in-depth analysis of the molecules detected in the grape samples revealed that more than 89% of them are developmental and reproductive toxins, with over 43% classified as carcinogenic and more than 36% as genotoxic (Annexe I - Figure SII-5). Indeed , the teratogenicity, carcinogenicity and potential to act as an endocrine disrupter as well as other health impacts of the detected molecules (Annexe I - Figure SII-5), explain the high and moderate human health alerts obtained in around 45 and 55 % of the instances respectively as shown in Figure II-5. Moreover, the occurrence of pesticide cocktails as discussed aggravate the notorious effect of these residues on human health. Since pesticides with analogous functions can exacerbate their deleterious effects through mechanisms such as dose/concentration addition, response addition, or cumulative biological effects, including synergistic augmentation and antagonistic effects (WHO 2018, Gamet-Payrastre 2019).

Degradability in Soil: DT50 (days) <20 : RD, Readily Degradable; 20–60 : FD, Fairly Degradable; 60–180 :SD, Slightly Degradable, >180: VSD, Very Slightly Degradable (FAO 2000; Lewis et al. 2016)
Potential for Movement Toward Groundwater: GUS Index < 0: Extremely Low; 0 – 1.8: Low; 1.8 – 2.8: Moderate; > 2.8 High; NA (Not Applicable) (Goss 1992; Lewis et al. 2016)
Bioaccumulation Potential: BCF (L/Kg) < 1000: NB, Not Bioaccumulative; 1000-5000 B, Bioaccumulative; >5000 VB, Very Bioaccumulative (Lewis et al. 2016; Rosioru et al. 2016)
 **Environmental Fate Alerts, Human Health Alerts and Ecotoxicity Alerts as per Lewis et al. 2016.

Figure II- 5: Assessment of alert levels in terms of environmental fate, human health and ecotoxicity for the detected pesticides in 2012, 2013, and 2014

Human Risk Assessment: Adults and Children

The health risk assessment reveals that all Hazard Quotients (HQs) obtained for each of the detected molecules across a three-year period were below 1 for both adults and children (Table II-3), indicating a negligible risk to human health. Notably, in the years 2013 and 2014, there was a general decline in HQ values for most molecules when compared to those recorded in 2012 excepting for chlorpyrifos, difenocazole, dimethoate, Hexaconazole, Indoxacarb, and thiophanate methyl. It is worth emphasizing the considerably high HQ values for adults and children associated with chlorpyrifos, surpassing those of all other molecules. Aligning to these results, Khazaal et al. (2022) showed that the majority of foods of plant origin in Beirut were safe with residues having HQs <1 except for chlorpyrifos residues in cucumber (1.8). El Hawari et al. (2019) also calculated high HQ for chlorpyrifos on apples. It is, however, important to note that our HQ calculations take into account the quantities of pesticides provided by the ingestion of grapes, without taking into account other foodstuffs which may also provide these same molecules.

Table II- 3: Assessment of health risk parameters: estimated daily intake (EDI), acceptable daily intake (ADI) and hazard quotient (HQ) for adults and children

Molecule	Year	Mean (mg.kg ⁻¹)	ADI* (mg.kg ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹)	EDI _{adult} ** (mg.kg ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹)	EDI _{children} ** (mg.kg ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹)	HQ _{adult}	HQ _{children}
Acetamidrid	2012	0.28	0.025	2.78E-05	2.24E-04	0.0011	0.009
	2013	0.24		2.46E-05	1.98E-04	0.0010	0.0079
	2014	0.13		1.35E-05	1.09E-04	0.0005	0.0043
Azoxystrobin	2012	0.46	0.2	4.59E-05	3.69E-04	0.0002	0.0018
	2013	0.19		1.95E-05	1.57E-04	0.0001	0.0008
	2014	0.12		1.19E-05	9.57E-05	0.0001	0.0005
Boscalid	2012	1.27	0.04	1.28E-04	1.03E-03	0.0032	0.0258
	2013	0.10		1.01E-05	8.15E-05	0.0003	0.002
	2014	0.33		3.31E-05	2.66E-04	0.0008	0.0067
Carbendazim	2012	0.95	0.02	9.58E-05	7.71E-04	0.0048	0.0385
	2013	0.31		3.12E-05	2.51E-04	0.0016	0.0126
	2014	0.30		3.03E-05	2.44E-04	0.0015	0.0122
Carbofuran	2012	0.01	0.00015	8.06E-07	6.49E-06	0.0054	0.0433
Chlorpyrifos	2012	0.24	0.001	2.45E-05	1.97E-04	0.0245	0.1972
	2013	0.33		3.35E-05	2.69E-04	0.0335	0.2693
	2014	0.43		4.30E-05	3.46E-04	0.0430	0.3459
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	2012	0.14	0.01	1.43E-05	1.15E-04	0.0014	0.0115
Cymoxanil	2012	0.01	0.013	8.97E-07	7.22E-06	0.0001	0.0006
Cypermethrin	2012	0.44	0.05	4.47E-05	3.60E-04	0.0009	0.0072
	2013	0.28		2.83E-05	2.28E-04	0.0006	0.0046
	2014	0.37		3.73E-05	3.00E-04	0.0007	0.006
Cyproconazole	2012	0.08	0.02	8.47E-06	6.81E-05	0.0004	0.0034
	2013	0.01		7.84E-07	6.31E-06	0.0000	0.0003
Cyprodinil	2012	0.39	0.03	3.89E-05	3.13E-04	0.0013	0.0104
	2013	0.17		1.69E-05	1.36E-04	0.0006	0.0045
	2014	0.30		3.04E-05	2.45E-04	0.0010	0.0082
Deltamethrin	2012	0.16	0.01	1.65E-05	1.33E-04	0.0017	0.0133
Difenoconazole	2012	0.08	0.01	8.24E-06	6.63E-05	0.0008	0.0066
	2013	0.12		1.18E-05	9.48E-05	0.0012	0.0095
	2014	1.47		1.48E-04	1.19E-03	0.0148	0.1189
Diflubenzuron	2012	0.01	0.1	8.06E-07	6.49E-06	0.0000	0.0001
Dimethoate	2012	0.08	0.001	7.72E-06	6.21E-05	0.0077	0.0621
	2013	0.08		8.52E-06	6.85E-05	0.0085	0.0685
	2014	0.13		1.35E-05	1.09E-04	0.0135	0.1087
Dimethomorph	2012	0.04	0.05	4.03E-06	3.24E-05	0.0001	0.0006
	2013	0.03		2.55E-06	2.05E-05	0.0001	0.0004
Etozazole	2012	0.09	0.04	9.07E-06	7.30E-05	0.0002	0.0018
Fenhexamid	2012	0.64	0.2	6.47E-05	5.20E-04	0.0003	0.0026
	2013	0.48		4.86E-05	3.91E-04	0.0002	0.002
	2014	0.46		4.66E-05	3.75E-04	0.0002	0.0019
Fluzifop-butyl	2012	0.01	NA	9.07E-07	7.30E-06	NA	NA
Flufenoxuron	2012	0.27	0.01	2.71E-05	2.18E-04	0.0027	0.0218
Flusilazole	2012	0.19	0.002	1.91E-05	1.54E-04	0.0095	0.0768
	2013	0.11		1.06E-05	8.54E-05	0.0053	0.0427
	2014	0.05		5.39E-06	4.34E-05	0.0027	0.0217
Hexaconazole	2012	0.02	0.005	1.75E-06	1.41E-05	0.0004	0.0028
	2013	0.01		6.79E-07	5.47E-06	0.0001	0.0011
	2014	0.10		9.90E-06	7.97E-05	0.0020	0.0159
Imidacloprid	2012	0.42	0.06	4.25E-05	3.42E-04	0.0007	0.0057
	2013	0.28		2.86E-05	2.30E-04	0.0005	0.0038
	2014	0.24		2.45E-05	1.98E-04	0.0004	0.0033

Indoxacarb	2012	0.26	5.0E-3	2.59E-05	2.08E-04	0.0052	0.0417
	2013	0.13		1.28E-05	1.03E-04	0.0026	0.0206
	2014	0.33		3.36E-05	2.71E-04	0.0067	0.0541
Kresoxim-methyl	2012	0.65	0.4	6.57E-05	5.29E-04	0.0002	0.0013
	2013	0.54		5.41E-05	4.36E-04	0.0001	0.0011
	2014	0.28		2.85E-05	2.29E-04	0.0001	0.0006
Lufenuron	2012	0.14	0.015	1.39E-05	1.12E-04	0.0009	0.0074
	2013	0.39		3.93E-05	3.16E-04	0.0026	0.0211
	2014	0.29		2.94E-05	2.37E-04	0.0020	0.0158
Metalaxyl	2012	0.18	0.08	1.79E-05	1.44E-04	0.0002	0.0018
	2014	0.13		1.29E-05	1.04E-04	0.0002	0.0013
Metalaxyl-M	2012	0.20		2.00E-05	1.61E-04	0.0002	0.002
Methamidophos	2012	0.15	4.0E-3	1.51E-05	1.22E-04	0.0038	0.0304
Methiocarb	2014	0.00	1.2E-2	4.23E-07	3.41E-06	0.0000	0.0003
Methomyl	2012	0.18	0.0025	1.80E-05	1.45E-04	0.0072	0.0581
Myclobutanil	2012	0.30	0.025	3.07E-05	2.47E-04	0.0012	0.0099
	2013	0.20		2.02E-05	1.63E-04	0.0008	0.0065
	2014	0.23		2.27E-05	1.83E-04	0.0009	0.0073
Penconazole	2012	0.10	0.03	1.05E-05	8.44E-05	0.0003	0.0028
	2013	0.06		6.45E-06	5.19E-05	0.0002	0.0017
	2014	0.09		8.92E-06	7.18E-05	0.0003	0.0024
Pirimiphos-methyl	2012	0.00	0.004	3.02E-07	2.43E-06	0.0001	0.0006
Procymidone	2012	0.01	0.0028	6.18E-07	4.98E-06	0.0002	0.0018
Propargite	2012	2.40	7.0E-3	2.42E-04	1.95E-03	0.0346	0.2781
Propiconazole	2013	0.00	0.04	1.61E-07	1.30E-06	0.0000	0
	2014	0.01		5.09E-07	4.10E-06	0.0000	0.0001
Pyraclostrobin	2012	0.24	0.03	2.45E-05	1.97E-04	0.0008	0.0066
	2014	0.08		7.79E-06	6.27E-05	0.0003	0.0021
Pyridaben	2012	0.03	0.01	3.48E-06	2.80E-05	0.0003	0.0028
	2013	0.01		6.49E-07	5.22E-06	0.0001	0.0005
	2014	0.01		9.64E-07	7.76E-06	0.0001	0.0008
Pyrimethanil	2012	0.59	0.17	5.90E-05	4.75E-04	0.0003	0.0028
	2013	0.09		9.53E-06	7.67E-05	0.0001	0.0005
	2014	0.40		4.05E-05	3.26E-04	0.0002	0.0019
Tebuconazole	2013	0.09	0.03	8.67E-06	6.98E-05	0.0003	0.0023
Tetraconazole	2012	0.16	0.004	1.65E-05	1.33E-04	0.0041	0.0332
	2013	0.15		1.49E-05	1.20E-04	0.0037	0.0299
	2014	0.08		8.08E-06	6.50E-05	0.0020	0.0163
Thiamethoxam	2013	0.46	2.5E-2	4.68E-05	3.76E-04	0.0018	0.0145
Thiophanate-methyl	2012	0.62	0.08	6.21E-05	5.00E-04	0.0008	0.0062
	2013	1.44		1.45E-04	1.17E-03	0.0018	0.0146
	2014	1.23		1.24E-04	1.00E-03	0.0016	0.0125
Tolclofos-methyl	2012	0.52	0.064	5.21E-05	4.20E-04	0.0008	0.0066
Triadimenol	2012	1.40	0.05	1.41E-04	1.14E-03	0.0028	0.0227
Trifloxystrobin	2012	0.04	0.1	4.17E-06	3.35E-05	0.0000	0.0003
	2013	0.07		6.67E-06	5.36E-05	0.0001	0.0005
	2014	0.11		1.09E-05	8.79E-05	0.0001	0.0009

*ADI : Acceptable Daily Intake retrieved from Lewis et al. 2016; **EDI: Estimated Daily Intake = $\sum \frac{F_i \times MR_i}{Bw}$: MRi =mean residual pesticide concentration; Fi : daily grape consumption data. Bw corresponds to the body weight of the consumer. For adults, a body weight of 63 kg and grape consumption of 0.00635 kg/day (EFSA). For children, a body weight of 16.15 kg and grape consumption of 0.0131 kg/day (EFSA).
 $HQ = \left(\frac{EDI}{ADI} \right)$; HQ >1 =Potential risk for human health.

Environmental Impact

In our study, molecules with DT50s in soils greater than 180 days were found in 18, 19 and 26 % of instances in 2012, 2013 and 2014, respectively (Figure II-5). This high persistency, has an adverse impact on the soil fertility by affecting its integrity, beneficial macrofauna and microflora and making it a repository to these chemicals (Aktar, Sengupta, and Chowdhury 2009). That further contributes to the emergence of resistances to pesticides. Additionally, our results indicated that throughout the three years, in 12 – 35 % of instances, the detected molecules had moderately to high potential to move toward groundwaters with GUS Index values varying from 1.8 to 2.8 or exceeding 2.8 in 12-14 % of the instances (Figure II-5). These findings are further showcased in the work of Youssef et al. in 2015 in Lebanon's South Litani River, their research brought attention to the long-lasting presence of prohibited pesticides, particularly organochlorines such as aldrin, heptachlor epoxide, and Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT), within both surface water and groundwater (Youssef et al. 2015). The leaching of these residues into ground and surface waters poses significant concerns, as it exacerbates toxic residues bioaccumulation through food cycle. This phenomenon is particularly alarming when these waters are utilized for irrigation purposes or when these residues become accumulated within aquatic organisms, such as fish. Similarly, Abou Zeid et al. (2020) and Akkoush and Halawani (2023) reported the presence of multiple residues in soils, surface waters, ground and drinking waters as well as honey samples.

Additionally, our results show that, throughout the three years the detected molecules had the potential to bioaccumulate in around 64 % of instance with bioconcentration factors (BCF) of 1000-5000 L/Kg. Additionally, in 18, 7 and 8 % of instances, the detected molecules had BCFs greater than 5000 L/Kg in 2012, 2013 and 2014, respectively, indicating a very bioaccumulative potential. Altogether, these results are reflected by the fact that the environmental fate alerts of the detected molecules as per Lewis et al. (2016)'s alert system, was high in around 46 % of instances and moderate in around 54 % of instances throughout the years. Similarly, for the ecotoxicity alerts that were considered as high in 62 % of instances and moderate in 38% of instances. These findings underscore the pressing necessity for more stringent environmental regulations in Lebanon, with a focus on mitigating the widespread use of pesticides. Specifically, banning the utilization of phytosanitary molecules characterized by high persistence in the environment.

4. Conclusion

The 2012-2014 monitoring data showed high frequency of pesticide residues in table grape, 56 to 97 % of positive samples with 15-33 % exceeding MRLs for one or more pesticide residues additionally to the usage of unrecommended molecules on grapes (>19%). Although phytosanitary practices may have improved nowadays, the findings of this study reflected the importance to train viticulturists in Lebanon to apply good agricultural practices and ensure safe products. Although the human risk assessment indicated no immediate health risks for adults and children, the consumption of grapes contributes to the overall exposure to residues of these molecules, in particular chlorpyrifos which presents the highest HQ values. Nevertheless, the HQ calculations only considered the exposure to residues through grapes consumption and do not encompass the exposure of individuals to these molecules from other food and non-food sources, as well as the exposure of viticulturists and/or pesticide applicators, thus do not reflect individuals' overall exposure to these residues or the potential hazards of synergistic, analogous, and additive effects from multiple residue exposures. . To add, the high incidences of residue cocktails raise concerns over human health and environmental impacts (pest resistance). The findings of this study showed that stringent regulations of pesticide use in Lebanon in particular in vineyards are imperative in order to reduce the risks for the human and environment health.

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